

Conflicts Strategies Involving the Pupils, Parents, and Teachers

Geronimo S. Bilbar Jr. MAEd

Public School Teacher, DepEd-Bayawan City Division, Bayawan City, Negros Oriental Philippines

I. INTRODUCTION

Conflict is widespread and universal in societies and their affairs. It occurs among organizations, within organizations, among the members of an organization and within the personality of each individual because presence of conflict is an everyday reality (Ayalew, 2000). This means, conflict is an inevitable and unavoidable concomitant of choices and decision aspects of human interaction (Miller, 2004).

Conflicts are normal segments of daily life; however, many conflicts may be considered to have negative effects as they cause disagreements, stress, social chaos, and violence (Dincyurek and Civelek, 2008). Differences in values and inconsistencies among educators and learners may also bring about disagreement between people (Calitz et al, 2002).

Each of us has a predominant conflict strategy that we use to meet our own needs. By examining conflict strategies and the consequences of those behaviors, we can gain a better understanding of the impact that our personal conflict strategies has on other people. With a better understanding, you then can make a conscious choice on how to respond to others in a conflict situation to help reduce work conflict and stress (Stevahn, 2004).

Furthermore, conflict occurs between people in all kinds of human relationships and social settings because of the wide-range of potential differences that people have. The absence of conflict usually signals the absence of meaningful interaction. Conflict by itself is neither good nor bad. However, the manner in which conflict is handled determines whether it is constructive or destructive (Owens, 2007).

Specifically, as far as conflict in schools is concerned, it varies from other conflict situations which appear in other organizations since different individuals and groups such as students, teachers, administrative workers and other stakeholders involve in school activities. All these stakeholders bring different ideas, goals, values and needs to their schools and primarily these differences affect the relationships and functions of school organizations. These differences inevitably lead to conflict. But, this does not necessarily mean that conflicts always result in negative consequences in organizations. They can provide considerable values and benefits to individuals and organizations. Conflicts, if constructively managed: increase cohesion, creativity and innovation, greater effort; improve organizational commitment and; reduce tension (Greenberg, 2006).

Based on these conditions, the researcher is interested to determine the conflict strategies involving the pupils, parents and teachers in Manduaw Elementary School, Bayawan City Division, Negros Oriental, hence, the conduct of this study.

II. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This was a descriptive research that utilized survey questionnaire. Descriptive Research, according to Travers (2000) is used to describe the nature of a situation as it exists at the time of the study and explore the causes of particular phenomena.

This study is described the nature of the situations that exist in public school in Manduaw Elementary School, Bayawan City Division, Negros Oriental as to the effective conflict strategies involving pupils, parents and teachers.

Research Respondents

Random sampling of the pupils and their parents and complete enumeration of teachers were the sampling of the study.

Research Instruments

This study was utilized a self-made and modified questionnaire to assess the effective conflict strategies involving pupils, parents and teachers. Part I is the pupils' strategies towards conflicts questionnaire comprising questions about conflicts strategies. Part II is the parents' strategies towards conflicts questionnaire comprising questions about conflicts strategies. Part III is the teachers' strategies towards conflicts questionnaire comprising questions about conflicts strategies and Part IV is the effective conflict strategies comprising questions about competing, collaborating, avoiding, accommodating and compromising.

Research Procedure

Upon the approval of the research, a letter of request is sent to the Dean of the Graduate Studies of Central Philippines State University asking permission to conduct the study for approval. The researcher sent another letter of request to the Division Superintendent thru the district supervisor to conduct the study for approval. Afterwards, a letter of the same purpose is sent to the principals asking permission to conduct the study. After which, administering the survey questionnaire will be followed accordingly to conduct the study. The data gathered will be retrieved immediately, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted by the researcher.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Extent of Pupils, Parents and Teachers’ Strategies towards Conflicts

Strategies Towards Conflict Types	Mean	Std. Deviation
Pupils	3.07	.530
Teachers	3.36	.653
Parents	3.10	.447
As a Whole	3.10	.545

4.21 – 5.00: *Always*
 3.41 – 4.20: *Often*
 2.61 – 3.40: *sometimes*
 1.81 – 2.60: *Rarely*
 1.00 – 1.80: *Never*

The table showed on the pupils, teachers and parents strategies towards conflicts.

As to teacher strategies towards conflicts, the highest mean score was 3.36 and had the standard deviation of .653 and interpreted as often then were followed by mean scores of 3.10, 3.07 respectively and had the standard deviation of 0.447, 0.530 and it were interpreted as often and as a whole the mean score was 3.10 and had the standard deviation of 0.545 and interpreted as often.

This means that the teachers, parents and pupils conflict strategies were manageable and understandable in the society.

Understanding the experiences of parents, teachers, and students in the presence of parent–teacher conflict related to a student’s abilities may provide insights about how to effectively resolve these conflicts. Research in this area could provide educators with the tools, knowledge, and skills necessary to resolve conflict and effectively partner with diverse families (Christenson, 2004).

Table 2.a. Extent of Conflict Strategies in Terms of Competing, Collaborating, Avoiding, Accommodating and Compromising on Pupils

CONFLICT STRATEGIES	PUPILS MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	INTERPRETATION
Competing	3.15	.807	Sometimes
Collaborating	3.01	.807	Sometimes
Avoiding	3.05	.842	Sometimes
Accommodating	2.90	.813	Sometimes
Compromising	3.08	.802	Sometimes

4.21 – 5.00: *Always*
 3.41 – 4.20: *Often*
 2.61 – 3.40: *sometimes*
 1.81 – 2.60: *Rarely*
 1.00 – 1.80: *Never*

Table 2a shows the extent of conflict strategies in terms of competing, collaborating, avoiding, accommodating and compromising weighted mean was utilized.

The extent of conflict strategies in terms of competing, collaborating, avoiding, accommodating and compromising on pupils

Based on the table presented it revealed that the conflict strategies in terms of competing, compromising, avoiding, collaborating and accommodating on pupils, mean results were 3.15, 3.08, 3.05, 3.01 and 2.90 respectively and the standard deviation of 0.807, 0.802, 0.842, 0.807 and 0.813 and they were interpreted as sometimes.

This means that the conflict strategies towards conflicts on pupils are sometimes observed and controlled.

The students usually will abide by a superior’s decision, whether or not the students agree with it. Specifically, it advocates the establishment of a superordinate- subordinate relationship (Kalagbor, 2003). Iwowari (2007) posits that the dominating strategy does not allow input from the students in the school system.

Table 2.b. Extent of Conflict Strategies in Terms of Competing, Collaborating, Avoiding, Accommodating and Compromising on Teachers

CONFLICT STRATEGIES	TEACHERS STANDARD INTERPRETATION		
	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	
Competing	3.48	.795	Often
Collaborating	3.00	.791	Sometimes
Avoiding	3.00	.750	Sometimes
Accommodating	3.42	.614	Often
Compromising	3.58	.867	Often

4.21 - 5.00: *Always*
 3.41 - 4.20: *Often*
 2.61 - 3.40: *sometimes*
 1.81 - 2.60: *Rarely*
 1.00 - 1.80: *Never*

Table 2b on the extent of conflict strategies in terms of competing, collaborating, avoiding, accommodating and compromising on teachers, weighted mean was utilized. The extent of conflict strategies in terms of competing, collaborating, avoiding, accommodating and compromising on teachers.

Based on the result presented, it revealed that the conflict strategies towards conflicts on teachers in terms of compromising has a mean score of 3.58 and has the standard deviation of 0.807 as often. It followed in terms of compromising and competing had the mean scores of 3.48 and 3.42 or 0.795 and 0.614 as often. Meanwhile, in terms of collaborating and avoiding and both had the mean scores of 3.00 and standard deviation of 0.791 and 0.750 as sometimes.

This means that the conflict strategies towards conflicts on teachers must engage competently in each strategy.

Principals effective utilization of the integrating approach or strategy may be as a result of the establishment of disciplinary committees by the principals in their various schools. This is a method that stimulate students, improves their sense of belonging, and allows fair hearing in the school system. According to Acholonu(1991), good administrators are concerned in stimulating members to take actions towards achieving describe goals.

Table 2.c. Extent of Conflict Strategies in Terms of Competing, Collaborating, Avoiding, Accommodating and Compromising on Parents

CONFLICT STRATEGIES	PARENTS MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	INTERPRETATION
Competing	3.00	.562	Sometimes
Collaborating	3.00	.791	Sometimes
Avoiding	2.90	.718	Sometimes
Accommodating	2.85	.671	Sometimes
Compromising	3.10	.447	Sometimes

4.21 - 5.00: Always
 3.41 - 4.20: Often
 2.61 - 3.40: sometimes
 1.81 - 2.60: Rarely
 1.00 - 1.80: Never

Based on the result presented, it revealed that the conflict strategies towards conflicts on parents in terms of compromising, competing, collaborating, avoiding and accommodating have mean scores of 3.10, 3.00, 3.00, 2.90 and 2.85 respectively and have the standard deviation of 0.447, 0.562, 0.791, 0.718 and 0.671 as sometimes.

This means that the conflict strategies towards conflicts on parents can solve problems that lead to conflict quickly. At other times, it can be hard to work out solutions.

The parent-child conflict is a function of the parent’s genetically-influenced tendency towards antisocial behavior then, the association between parent-child conflict and child antisocial behavior could thus be a reflection of common genes rather than the direct effects of shared-environmental influences (Neiderhiser et al., 2004,).

Table 3. Relationship between the Pupils’ Strategies towards Conflicts and Conflict Strategies in Terms of Competing, Collaborating, Avoiding, Accommodating and Compromising

Conflict Strategies	PUPILS’ STRATEGIES TOWARDS CONFLICTS			
	Sig. 0.05 level	R	Decision	Interpretation
Competing	.000	.475**	Reject H ₀	HS
Collaborating	.000	.455**	Reject H ₀	HS
Avoiding	.000	.488**	Reject H ₀	HS
Accommodating	.000	.395**	Reject H ₀	HS
Compromising	.000	.493**	Reject H ₀	HS

Sig. - Significant if p-value is lesser than 0.05
 Not. Sig. - Not Significant if p-value is greater than 0.05

Table 3 shows relationship between the pupils’ strategies towards conflicts and conflict strategies in terms of competing, collaborating, avoiding, accommodating and compromising Pearson-r was utilized. The relationship between the pupils’ strategies towards conflicts and conflict strategies in terms of competing, collaborating, avoiding, accommodating and compromising was examined.

Based on the result, it revealed that the conflict strategies in terms competing, collaborating, avoiding, accommodating and compromising have high significant relationship to pupils as p-value is lesser than 0.05.

This means to reject the hypothesis and concluded that there were significant relationships of conflict strategies towards pupils’ conflict strategies.

In research on the effects of conflict resolution training on elementary school students, about half of the students involved brought their conflicts to the teacher or applied what the authors assessed as destructive and ineffective strategies in handling conflicts (Atıcı, 2007).

It is absolutely necessary to manage the teacher- student conflict correctly in order to create a positive school climate and to conduct the education process effectively.

Table 4. Relationship between the Parents’ Strategies towards Conflicts and Conflict Strategies in Terms of Competing, Collaborating, Avoiding, Accommodating and Compromising

Conflict Strategies	PARENTS’ STRATEGIES TOWARDS CONFLICTS			
	Sig. 0.05 level	R	Decision	Interpretation
Competing	.073	.409	Accept H ₀	NS
Collaborating	.361	.216	Accept H ₀	NS
Avoiding	.020	.516*	Reject H ₀	S
Accommodating	.659	-.105	Accept H ₀	NS
Compromising	.000	.722**	Reject H ₀	HS

Sig. - Significant if p-value is lesser than 0.05
Not. Sig. - Not Significant if p-value is greater than 0.05

Table 4 shows relationship between parents’ strategies towards conflicts and conflict strategies in terms of competing, collaborating, avoiding, accommodating and compromising, Pearson-r was utilized.

The relationship between parents’ strategies towards conflicts and conflict strategies in terms of competing, collaborating, avoiding, accommodating and compromising was examined.

Based on the result, it revealed that the conflict strategies in terms of avoiding and compromising have significant relationship as to the parents’ conflict strategies.

This means to reject the hypothesis and concluded that there were significant relationships of conflict strategies towards parents’ conflict strategies as p-value is lesser than 0.05.

As to competing, collaborating and accommodating have no significant relationship on parents' conflict strategies as p-value is greater than 0.05.

This means to accept the hypothesis and concluded that there were no significant relationships of conflict strategies towards parents' conflict strategies.

Henderson, Mapp, Johnson, and Davies (2007) identified four core beliefs that must exist in schools to build meaningful partnerships with families. First, educators must believe that all parents have aspirations for their children and desire the best for them. Second, educators must believe that all parents have the ability to support their children's development and learning. The third necessary educator belief is that teachers view parents as equals.

Table 5. Relationship between the Teachers' Strategies towards Conflicts and Conflict Strategies in Terms of Competing, Collaborating, Avoiding, Accommodating and Compromising

Conflict Strategies	TEACHERS' STRATEGIES TOWARDS CONFLICTS			
	Sig. 0.05 level	R	Decision	Interpretation
Competing	.000	.610**	Reject H _o	HS
Collaborating	.000	.695**	Reject H _o	HS
Avoiding	.000	.720**	Reject H _o	HS
Accommodating	.005	.475**	Reject H _o	HS
Compromising	.000	.722**	Reject H _o	HS

Sig. - Significant if p-value is lesser than 0.05
Not. Sig. - Not Significant if p-value is greater than 0.05

Table 5 shows relationship between teachers' strategies towards conflicts and conflict strategies in terms of competing, collaborating, avoiding, accommodating and compromising Pearson-r was utilized

The relationship between teachers' strategies towards conflicts and conflict strategies in terms of competing, collaborating, avoiding, accommodating and compromising was examined.

Based on the result, it revealed that the conflict strategies in terms competing, collaborating, avoiding, accommodating and compromising have high significant relationship as to teachers as p-value is lesser than 0.05.

This means to reject the hypothesis and concluded that there were significant relationships of conflict strategies towards teachers' conflict strategies.

The teachers who defined conflicts as differences of opinion emphasized the concepts such as inability to find common ground, differences of opinion, inability to form unity in ideas, disagreements, having different views, clash of ideas and dissensus. For teachers who defined conflicts as negative situations emphasized the following concepts: forming groups with like minded people, tension, unconformity, harming others, communication gap, ideological disputes and prejudices. Findings suggest

that teachers still have the traditional approach towards the concept of conflicts because the majority of teachers consider conflicts as unnecessary and disturbing situations based on traditional view. Conflicts are considered to be phenomena that hinder the realization of school goals and that harm educators and students. Therefore the majority of teachers do not believe that conflicts at schools can create opportunities to resolve problems related to management. At the same time, meanings that were ascribed to the concept of conflict by teachers were found to be similar to those used in the literature (Şimşek, 2002; Koçel, 2003; Eren, 2003).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In light to these findings, the researcher concluded that the conflict strategies in terms of competing, collaborating, avoiding, accommodating and compromising have high significant relationship to pupils as p-value is lesser than 0.05.

This means to reject the hypothesis and concluded that there were significant relationships of conflict strategies towards pupils' conflict strategies.

Based on the result, it concluded that the conflict strategies in terms of avoiding and compromising have significant relationship as to the parents' conflict strategies.

This means to reject the hypothesis and concluded that there were significant relationships of conflict strategies towards parents' conflict strategies as p-value is lesser than 0.05.

As to competing, collaborating and accommodating have no significant relationship on parents' conflict strategies as p-value is greater than 0.05.

This means to accept the hypothesis and concluded that there were no significant relationships of conflict strategies towards parents' conflict strategies.

Based on the result, it concluded that the conflict strategies in terms competing, collaborating, avoiding, accommodating and compromising have high significant relationship as to teachers as p-value is lesser than 0.05.

This means to reject the hypothesis and concluded that there were significant relationships of conflict strategies towards teachers' conflict strategies.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the findings and conclusions, the researcher formulated the following recommendations:

1. In the classroom, create and maintain an atmosphere of openness and respect. Provide ample opportunities for students to share feelings without being judged negatively by others.
2. It is absolutely necessary to manage the teacher- student conflict correctly in order to create a positive school climate and to conduct the education process effectively.
3. Pupils must be aware and informed ahead of the school policies and classroom rules so that less conflict occurs.
4. Teachers have varied conflict strategies to solve the conflict raised by the students and parents.
5. Parents must be updated and involved during parent-teacher association meeting so that there's no conflict exists.

REFERENCES

- Allen, J., & Land, D. (1999). Attachment in adolescence. *Handbook of attachment: Theory, research, and clinical*. New York, NY: Guilford Press.
- Babbitt, E. (2006). Mediating rights-based conflicts: Making self-determination negotiable. *International Negotiation*, 11(1), 185-208.
- Babbitt, E., & Hampson, F. (2011). Conflict resolution as a field of inquiry: Practice informing theory. *International Studies Review*, 13(1), 46-57.
- Bandura, A. (1986). *Social foundation of thought and action: A social cognitive theory*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Beyers, P. Y. (1997). *Organizational communication: Theory and behavior*. Boston, MA: Allyn and Bacon.
- Blake, R. R., & Mouton, J.S. (1964). *The managerial grid*. Huston, TX: Gulf Publishing.
- Blake, R. R., & Mouton, J. S. (1970). The fifth achievement. *Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 6, 413-426.
- Boonsathorn, W. (2007). Understanding conflict management styles of Thais and Americans in multinational corporation in Thailand. *International Journal of Conflict Management*, 18, (3) 196-221.
- Bresnahan, M. J., Donohue, W., Shearman, S. M., & Guan, X. (2009). Research note: Two measures of conflict orientation. *Conflict Resolution Quarterly*, 26(3), 365-379.
- Breunlin, D. C., Cimmarusti, R. A., Bryant-Edwards, T. L., & Hetherington, J. S. (2002). Conflict resolution training as an alternative to suspension for violent behavior. *Journal of Educational Research*, 95(6), 349.
- Bush, R. A. & Folger, J. P. (1994). *The promise of mediation: Responding to conflict through empowerment and recognition*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Callanan, G. A., Benzing, C. D., & Perri, D. F. (2006). Choice of Conflict-Handling Strategy: A Matter of Context. *Journal Of Psychology*, 140(3), 269-288.
- Callanan, G. A., & Perri, D. F. (2006). Teaching Conflict Management Using a Scenario-Based Approach. *Journal of Education For Business*, 81(3), 131-139.
- Canary, D., Cupach, W., & Messman, S. (1995). *Relationship conflict*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications

- Canary, D. J., Cunningham, F. M., & Cody, M. J. (1988). Goal types, gender, and locus of control in managing interpersonal conflict. *Communication Research*, 15, 426-446.
- Corcoran, K. O. C., & Mallinckrodt, B. (2000). Adult attachment, self-efficacy, perspective talking, and conflict resolution. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 58, 644-663.
- Curall, S. C., Friedman, R. A., Tidd, S. T., & Tsai, J. C. (2000). What goes around comes around: The impact of personal conflict style on work and stress. *The International Journal of Conflict Management*, 11(1), 32-55.
- Deen, M. Y. (2000). Difference in the solution-oriented conflict style of selected groups of 4-H youth development volunteer leaders. *Journal of Extension*, 38(1), 2000.
- Dumlao, R., & Botta, R. A. (2000). Family communications patterns and the conflict styles young adults use with their fathers. *Communication Quarterly*, 48(2), 174-189.
- Dincyurek, S., & Civelek, A. H. (2008). The determination of the conflict resolution strategies of university students that they use when they have conflicts with people. *Behavior Analyst Today*, 9(3/4), 215-233. Influence of conflict resolution, Page 14 Research in Higher Education Journal Volume 28 – May, 2015
- Drew, N. (1987). *Learning the skills of peacemaking*. Rolling Hills Estates, CA: Jalmar Press.
- Eron, L. D., Gentry, J. H., & Schlegel, P. (1994). *Reason to hope: A psychological perspective on violence and youth*. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.
- Farrell, A. D., Meyer, A. L., E Kung, M., & Sullivan, T. N. (2001). Development and evaluation of school-bases violence prevention programs. *Journal of Clinical Child Psychology*, 30(2), 207-221.
- Fetherston, A. B. (1994). *Towards a theory of United Nations peacekeeping*. New York: St. Martin's Press.
- Friedman, R. A., Tidd, S. T., Currall, S. C., & Tsai, J. C. (2000). What around comes around: The impact of personal conflict styles on work conflict and job stress. *International Journal of Conflict management*, 11, 32-55.
- Gardner, P. D., & Lambert, S. (1992). *It's a hard, hard world!* East Lansing, MI: Michigan State University Collegiate Employment Research Institute.
- Greasey, G. (2002). Psychological distress in college-aged women: Links with unresolved preoccupied attachment status and mediating role of negative mood regulation expectancies. *Attachment and Human development*, 4, 261-277.
- Greasey, G. & Ladd, A. (2004). Negative mood regulation expectancies and conflict behavior in late adolescent college student romantic relationships: The moderating role of generalized

- attachment representations. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 14(2), 236-256.
- Hecht, M. L., Jackson, R. L., & Ribeau, S. A. (2003). *African American Communication: Exploring Identity and Culture*. Mahwah, N.J: Erlbaum.
- Holt, J. L. & DeVore, C. J. (2005). Culture, gender, organizational role, and style of conflict resolution: A meta-analysis. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 29, 165- 196.
- Janeja, D. K. (2011). *The impact of family communication pattern on young adults conflict styles with their parents*. ProQuest Dissertation
- Jehn, K. A. (1997). A qualitative analysis of conflict types and dimensions in organizational groups. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 42, 530-557.
- Johnson, P. (1994). Conflict management: A review of the literature for school leaders. *Journal of School Leadership*, 4, 709-725.
- Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. (1996). Conflict resolution and peer mediation programs in elementary and secondary schools: A review of the research. *Review of Educational Research*, 66, 459–506.
- Johnson, D. W., Johnson, R., Dudley, B., Mitchell, J., & Fredrickson, J. (1997). The impact of conflict resolution training on middle school students. *Journal of Social Psychology*, 137(1), 11-21.
- Kriesberg, L. (1997). *Preventing and resolving destructive communal conflict. In the international politics of ethnic conflict: Theory and Evidence*. Pittsburgh: University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Mattingly, B. (2009). *Help increase the peace program*. Baltimore, MD: Middle Atlantic Region, American Friends Service Committee.
- Moberg, P. J. (2001). Linking conflict strategy to the five factor model. Theoretical and empirical foundations. *International journal of Conflict Management*, 12(1), 47-68.
- Goldsworthy, R., Schwartz, N., Barab, S., & Landa, A. (2007). Evaluation of a collaborative multimedia conflict resolution curriculum. *Educational Technology, Research and Development*, 55, 5, 597-625. Influence of conflict resolution, Page 15 Research in Higher Education Journal Volume 28 – May, 2015
- Moberg, P. J. (1998). Predicting conflict strategies with personality trait: Incremental validity and the five factor model. *International Journal of conflict management*, 9(3), 258-285.
- Morrison, M., Shaw Austad, C., & Cota, K. (2011). Help increase the peace, a youth-focused program in peace education. *Journal of Peace Education*, 8(2), 177-191.

- Mukhtar, S. & Habib, M. N. (2010). Private Sector managers approach to conflict management: A study of relationships between conflict management styles and personality type. Interdisciplinary. *Journal of Contemporary Research Business*, 2,1, 304-312.
- Noore, N. M. (2006). Locus of control, supportive workplace policies and work family conflict. *Psychologia*, 49, 48-60.
- Palmer, C., & Roessler, R. T. (2000). Requesting classroom accommodations: Self-advocacy and conflict Resolution training for college students with disabilities. *Journal of Rehabilitation*, 66(3), 38-43.
- Pistole, M. C., & Arricale, F. (2003). Understanding attachment: Beliefs about conflict. *Journal of Counseling and Development*, 81, 318-328.
- Pondy, L. R. (1992). Reflections on organizational conflict. *Journal of Organisational Behaviour* 13(2), 257-61.
- Putnam, L. L. & Wilson, C. (1982). *Communicative strategies in organizational conflict. Reliability and validity of a measurement scale. Communication Yearbook*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Rahim, M. A. (2000). Empirical studies on handling conflict. *International Journal of conflict Management*, 11, 5-8.
- Rahim, M. A. (1992). *Managing conflict on organizations*. Westport, CT: Praeger Publishers. Rahim, M. A., & Bonoma, T. V. (1979). Managing organizational conflict: A model for diagnosis and intervention. *Psychology Reports*, 44, 1323-1344.
- Rahim, M. A., & Buntzman, G. F. (1989). Supervisory power bases, styles of handling conflict with subordinates, and subordinate compliance and satisfaction. *The Journal of Psychology*, 123(2), 195-210.
- Robbins, S. P. (1988). *Essential of organizational behaviors*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-hall.
- Sierau, S., & Herzberg, P. Y. (2012). Conflict resolution as a Dyadic mediator: Considering the partner perspective on conflict resolution. *European Journal of Personality*, 26, 221-232. Simerly, R. G. (1998). Managing conflict for productive results: A critical leadership skill. *The Journal of Continuing Higher Education*, 46, 2-11.
- Shockley-Zalabak, P. (1981). The effects of sex difference on the preference for utilization of conflict styles of managers in a work setting: An exploratory study. *Public Personal Management Journal*, 10, 289-295.
- Stevahn, L. (2004). Integrating conflict resolution training into the curriculum. *Theory Into Practice*, 43(1), 50-58.
- Stevahn, L., Johnson, D. W., Johnson, R. T., & Schultz, R. (2002). Effects of conflict resolution

- training integrated into a high school social studies curriculum. *Journal of Social Psychology*, 142(3), 305-331.
- Sweeney, B., & Carruthers, W. L. (1996). Conflict resolution: History, philosophy, theory, and educational applications. *The School Counselor*, 43(5), 326-344.
- Taylor, M. (2010). Does locus of conflict predict young adults conflict strategies wit superiors? An examination of control orientation and the organization communication conflict instrument. *North American Journal of Psychology*, 12(3), 445-458.
- Thomas, K. W. (1976). Toward multi-dimensional values in teaching: The example of conflict behaviors. *Academy of Management Review*, 2, 484-490.
- Ting-Toomey, S., & Chung, L. C. (2005). *Understanding Intercultural Communication*. Los Angeles, CA: Roxbury.
- Warters, W. C (1999). *Mediation in the campus community: Designing and maintaining effective programs*. San Francisco: CA. Jossey-Bass Publishers.
- Wall, J., & Druckman, D. (2002, June). *Mediation in peacekeeping missions. Paper presented at the International Association for Conflict Management conference*, Park City, UT.
- Weitzman, P. F. & Weitzman, E. A. (2006). Brief report: Promoting post formal thinking on the job: A protocol for interpersonal conflict resolution training. *Journal of Adult Development*, 13, 45-51.
- Wilson, S. R., & Waltman, M. S. (1988). Assessing the Putnam-Wilson organization communication conflict instrument. *Management Communication Quarterly*, 1, 367-388. Womack, D. F (1988). Assessing the Thomas-Kilmann conflict mode survey: Conceptualization. *Management Communication Quarterly*, (1) 3, 321-362.
- Zimmer-Gembeck, M. (2002). The development of romantic relationships and adaptations in the system of peer relationships. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 31, 216-225.

APPENDICES

RESEARCH SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

“EFFECTIVE CONFLICT STRATEGIES INVOLVING THE PUPILS, PARENTS AND TEACHERS”

PART I. PUPILS’ STRATEGIES TOWARDS CONFLICTS SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Rate each statement on a scale of 1 to 5 indicating how likely you are to use this strategy.

1 = Never 2= Rarely 3 = Sometimes 4 = Often 5 = Always

Pupils’ Strategies					
1. If two friends are arguing, I try to understand both sides of the argument.					
2. I can think of several different ways to deal with a disagreement.					
3. I have thought about how I normally respond to conflicts.					
4. I feel good about I handle most conflicts or disagreements.					
5. The ways I try to resolve conflicts work for me.					
6. In an argument, I try to understand the other person’s point of view.					
7. I respond to different disagreements differently.					
8. When someone is upset with me, I try to find out why.					
9. I try to figure out if someone is arguing just because they’re in a bad mood.					
10. Instead jumping to conclusions, I try to figure out why there’s an agreement.					
11. I try to understand if a disagreement is caused by a misunderstanding.					
12. If I’m mad at a friend, I avoid talking to her or her.					
13. I try to find win-win solutions to disagreement.					
14. When someone is disagree with someone, I talk about how I feel and listen to them talk about how they feel					
15. When I’m involved in a disagreement, I stop and think about what I say or do.					
16. During a disagreement I try to find a compromise.					
17. If I’m angry with someone, I try to stay clam when we’re talking.					
18. I try to win every argument even if I lose friends over it.					
19. When I disagree with someone, I try to talk it through with them					
20. When I disagree with someone, I defend my position but I don’t put the other person down in the process.					

PART II. PARENTS' STRATEGIES TOWARDS CONFLICTS SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Rate each statement on a scale of 1 to 5 indicating how likely you are to use this strategy.

1 = Never 2 = Rarely 3 = Sometimes 4 = Often 5 = Always

Parents' Strategies					
1. When someone else thinks they have a good idea I cooperate and help them.					
2. If people don't respect my opinion, I keep it to myself.					
3. I often slight modifications in my goals to meet other peoples' needs.					
4. I am always to listen to other's opinion, but I also want to give them mine.					
5. I need to attain solutions of the problems and cannot be limited by others.					
6. When conflicts arise, I usually stand on my principles.					
7. I am always willing to consider other people's opinions, but I make my own decisions.					
8. When a conflict arises, I am usually willing to adjust my priorities to reach a resolution.					
9. When conflict occurs, I tend to back out of the situation and do something else.					
10. I don't like to rock the boat, so I cooperate with others and accept instructions easily.					
11. When pursuing my priorities am usually firm and not swayed by others.					
12. During conflict, I immediately work to get everyone's concerns out in the open.					
13. During a conflict, I try to find someone to compromise.					
14. Differences of opinion are not always worth worrying about, so I usually avoid them.					
15. I like to ask others for their opinions and try to find ways to cooperate.					
16. I am a decision maker, but I make a point of listening to others to find the best solution possible.					
17. After I have made a decision, I defend it strongly.					
18. I think it is important to get along than to win an argument.					
19. I often keep to myself, because most things are not worth arguing about.					
20. I try to adjust the priorities to accommodate other people's needs.					

PART III. TEACHERS' STRATEGIES TOWARDS CONFLICTS SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Rate each statement on a scale of 1 to 5 indicating how likely you are to use this strategy.

1 = Never 2 = Rarely 3 = Sometimes 4 = Often 5 = Always

Teachers' Strategies					
1. The case was argued with them to show the merits of his position.					
2. There was negotiation so that, a compromise can be reached.					
3. To try to satisfy their expectations.					
4. To try to investigate the issue in conflict so as to find a solution acceptable to them.					
5. To be firm in pursuing the side of the issue.					
6. To attempt to avoid being "put on the spot" and try to keep a conflict with them to oneself.					
7. To hold on to the solution to the problem.					
8. To use "give and take" so that, a compromise can be reached.					
9. To exchange accurate information with them in view to solved the problem together.					
10. To avoid an open discussion of some differences with them.					
11. To accommodate their wishes and move on.					
12. To try to bring all their concerns out in the open so that the issues can be resolved in the best possible way.					
13. To propose a middle ground for breaking deadlocks.					
14. To go along with their suggestions.					
15. To try to keep a disagreement with them to oneself in order to avoid hard feelings.					

PART IV. CONFLICT STRATEGIES QUESTIONNAIRE

RESEARCH SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

“THE CONFLICT STRATEGIES INVOLVING THE PUPILS, PARENTS AND TEACHERS”

Each statement below provides a strategy for dealing with a conflict. Rate each statement on a scale of 1 to 5 indicating how likely you are to use this strategy.

1 = Never 2= Rarely 3 = Sometimes 4 = Often 5 = Always

Conflict Strategies					
1. I explore issues with others so as to find solutions that meet everyone’s needs.					
2. I try to negotiate and adopt a give-and-take approach to problem situations.					
3. I try to meet the expectations of others.					
4. I would argue my case and insist on the merits of my point of view.					
5. When there is a disagreement, I gather as much information as I can and keep the lines of communication open.					
6. When I find myself in an argument, I usually say very little and try to leave as soon as possible.					
7. I try to see conflicts from both sides. What do I need? What does the other person Need? What are the issues involved?					
8. I prefer to compromise when solving problems and just move on.					
9. I find conflicts challenging and exhilarating; I enjoy the battle of wits that usually follows.					
10. Being at odds with other people makes me feel uncomfortable and anxious.					
11. I try to accommodate the wishes of my friends and family.					
12. I can figure out what needs to be done and I am usually right.					
13. To break deadlocks, I would meet people halfway.					
14. I may not get what I want but it’s a small price to pay for keeping the peace.					
15. I avoid hard feelings by keeping my disagreements with others to myself.					

THANK YOU ONCE AGAIN!!!